

National Research Programme “Energy Turnaround” (NRP 70)

ACTIVE INTERFACES – Holistic strategy to simplify standards, assessments and certification for building integrated photovoltaics

SNF project 153849

Energy-Policy analysis

Report 2/3

30. 06. 2016

Erarbeitet durch

econcept AG, Gerechtigkeitsgasse 20, CH-8002 Zürich
www.econcept.ch / + 41 44 286 75 75

Autoren/innen

Meta Lehmann, MA in Germanistik und Volkswirtschaftslehre
Walter Ott, lic. oec. publ. UZH, Ökonom, dipl. El. Ing. ETH, Raumplaner ETH/NDS

Inhalt

1	Introduction	1
2	Policy review	2
2.1	Overview	2
2.2	Energy Strategy 2050	3
2.2.1	Initial package of measures: Fostering energy conservation and deployment of renewable energy in buildings	3
2.2.2	Long term strategy: transition from subsidies to taxes	5
2.3	National laws and policy instruments	5
2.3.1	PV installation on roofs without building permit	5
2.3.2	Feed-in remuneration at cost	6
2.3.3	One-off investment grants	7
2.3.4	Self-consumption	8
2.3.5	Purchase guarantee	8
2.4	Model regulations of the cantons for energy matters (MuKEEn/MoPEC)	9
2.4.1	MuKEEn/MoPEC 2008 and PV	9
2.4.2	MuKEEn/MoPEC 2014 and PV	9
2.4.3	MuKEEn/MoPEC 2014: Implications for BIPV	10
2.5	Support for PV by the cantons	11
2.6	International regulations and trends	12
3	Trends and goals for future policies	14
3.1	Future financial support for PV	14
3.2	Storage as the new topic	14
3.3	Passing on of grid costs	15
4	Policy assumptions for Active Interfaces	16
	Literatur	18

1 Introduction

«Active Interfaces» explores holistic operational strategies overcoming obstacles for large-scale advanced photovoltaic integration into urban renewal and building renovation processes. To foster widespread deployment of **building integrated PV** solutions (BIPV), in «Active Interfaces» the subsequent operational goals are pursued:

- Clear identification of the different relevant operational barriers at technical, spatial, design and socio-economic levels.
- Development of alternative strategic approaches for BIPV in urban renewal and building renovation processes - from industrial production to implementation by end users (with optimal equilibrium between demand and supply).
- Concrete test and optimization of these new approaches for BIPV on real case studies of urban renewal processes.
- Establishment of recommendations to foster the implementation practice of BIPV-solutions in Switzerland.

Within «Active Interfaces», BIPV-solutions will be developed for archetypal buildings and case studies. Resulting impacts of BIPV-solutions on energy generation and consumption, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and costs will be assessed and compared with renewal and renovation solutions not applying BIPV solutions.

The current standards, assessments, certifications, life-cycle inventories and policies valid for buildings and PV modules for building integration are reviewed for being obstacle or promoter of BIPV. The paper at hand gives a short overview on existing policies on cantonal, national and international level. On the basis of yet perceivable trends it also proposes assumptions on future policy developments that might be relevant for BIPV.

In addition to the «Common methodological framework to assess energy, climate and economic impacts of BIPV» (econcept, 30.6.2016) this paper aims to define common assumptions concerning the policy environment for the assessment of the BIPV-solutions within the «Active Interfaces» project. Policies concerning technical aspects like technical requirements, fire safety regulations and similar matters will not be part of the present report. For these aspects we refer to project 04, workpackage 1.3 of SUPSI containing reviews of certifications for BIPV.

This research project is part of the National Research Programme «Energy Turnaround» (NRP 70) of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF). Further information on the National Research Programme can be found at www.nrp70.ch.

The present report 2 of econcept in Project 04 of Active Interfaces is complemented by the subsequent two reports:

- Report 1: «Common methodological frame-work to assess energy, climate and economic impacts of BIPV », 30.6. 2016
- Report 3: «Significance of prevailing regulations, standards and labels for the deployment of BIPV», 14.12. 2017

2 Policy review

2.1 Overview

The Swiss Energy Strategy 2050 is the framework for the actual and future energy policies in Switzerland. The following figure illustrates this framework and the corresponding laws and planned measures. In the following chapters this framework will be discussed focusing on issues concerning photovoltaic (PV) installation and the promotion of photovoltaic power production.

Figure 1: Framework of energy policies in Switzerland based on the Swiss Energy Strategy 2050

2.2 Energy Strategy 2050

In the wake of the nuclear accident of Fukushima, the Federal Council and the Parliament decided in 2011 that Switzerland is to withdraw from the use of nuclear energy on a step-by-step basis. The Swiss energy system will therefore require successive restructuring in the time period up to 2050. In view of this, the Federal Council has developed a long-term Swiss energy policy «Energy Strategy 2050»¹. Energy Strategy 2050 focuses on the consistent exploitation of the existing energy efficiency potentials and on the balanced use of the potentials of hydropower and new renewable energy sources².

Subsequently we will focus on the policy goals that affect photovoltaic installations and photovoltaic power production.

The net power production of Switzerland in 2012 was 66 TWh, 3% of it from new renewable energies (sun, biomass, biogas, wind, waste³). This means about 2 TWh/a production from new renewable energies. The Energie Strategy 2050 sets the goal of 24.2 TWh/a electricity production from renewable energies (except water power) by 2050 or 14.5 TWh/a by the year 2035.

2.2.1 Initial package of measures: Fostering energy conservation and deployment of renewable energy in buildings

In September 2013 the Federal Council submitted an initial package of measures in line with the Energie Strategie 2050 to parliament for discussion. The National Council and the Council of States approved the package of measures on 8 December 2014 and on 23 September 2015, respectively. Currently the two Councils are in the process of resolving their differences regarding the measures before they both vote again on the entire bill.

Chapter 4.2.6 of the Federal Council's dispatch text concerning the initial package of measures focuses on measures to foster deployment of renewable energy⁴.

The feed-in remuneration at cost (FRC, in German: Kostendeckende Einspeisevergütung KEV) for electricity from renewable energy sources like photovoltaics (PV) should be optimised and act closer to market conditions. The additional grid fee shall be increased (to 2.3 ct./kWh) to generate more funds for this promotion instrument to support more installations but for a period of 15 years only. Whether the feed-in remuneration will be replaced by a system in which the producers with controllable installations don't get a fixed price but have to negotiate with the buyers and produce electricity when it is needed or whether the feed-in remuneration system is more or less kept but limited to six more years is not decided yet. The two Councils differ on this point and have to find a compromise.

¹ 13.074 Botschaft zum ersten Massnahmenpaket der Energiestrategie 2050 (Revision des Energierechts) und zur Volksinitiative «Für den geordneten Ausstieg aus der Atomenergie (Atomausstiegsinitiative)» vom 4. September 2013

² <http://www.bfe.admin.ch/themen/00526/00527/index.html?lang=en> (status quo 15.12.2015)

³ Wind, bio mass and sun contribute only 1.1 percent of the net production.

⁴ 13.074 Botschaft zum ersten Massnahmenpaket der Energiestrategie 2050 (Revision des Energierechts) und zur Volksinitiative «Für den geordneten Ausstieg aus der Atomenergie (Atomausstiegsinitiative)» vom 4. September 2013

It is not clear yet whether the PV power production will be judged as controllable and therefore apt to take part in the negotiation scheme (see also chapter 2.3.2 Feed-in remuneration at cost). According to Art. 24 of the draft of the new energy law the Federal Council would be allowed to define installation types that do not have to take part in the market premium scheme. But the Council of States wants this article to be deleted. According to the Council of States the power cap for the one-off investment grants is to be deleted too at the same time (Art. 28a). The one-off investment grants according to the initial package of measures of Energy Strategy 2050 are already implemented but with a cap at 30 kW_{peak} (see also chapter 2.3.3 «One-off investment grants»).

The explicit right of self-consumption of on-site generated PV electricity is also mentioned in the initial package of measures and is already implemented.

The package of measures also mentions the following facilitations for PV-installations, which are already implemented:

- RPG Art. 18a⁵: PV-Installations that are appropriately fitted to a roof do not need a building permit any more. They just have to be reported to the authorities (nevertheless affected neighbours may object against the installation of such PV modules). Installations on historical or cultural monuments still need a building permit but which can only be denied if the monument is essentially affected.
- VPeA, SR 734.25⁶: PV installations smaller than 30 kVA⁷ don't need to pass an approval process for electric installations any more.

Chapter 4.2.1 of the Federal Council's dispatch text concerning the initial package of measures focuses on measures to promote energy efficiency in buildings.

If possible from 2020 onwards new buildings should use all year round heating energy from renewable sources and partly on-site produced electricity. The rate of energy related renovations of old buildings shall be increased significantly. For this purpose the CO₂-tax will be increased to intensify the promotion of building renovation. Energy relevant building renovations will be promoted by CHF 525 Mio. per year (Gebäudeprogramm: CHF 350 Mio. p.a. from the Federation, CHF 175 Mio. p.a. from the cantons). The original time limit of the subsidy program will be removed in order to guarantee a smooth transition from the promotion scheme to a scheme of management of demand via financial tax incentives planned thereafter.

Since PV installations are often implemented at the occasion of a building renovation, the increase in funds to subsidise energy related building renovation also serves (BI)PV. But since BIPV requires more planning effort and higher initial investments than PV, BIPV will often be the second choice when it is integrated in energy related building renovation measures,

⁵ Bundesgesetz über die Raumplanung (Raumplanungsgesetz, RPG) vom 22. Juni 1979 (Stand am 1. Mai 2014)

⁶ 734.25 Verordnung über das Plangenehmigungsverfahren für elektrische Anlagen (VPeA) vom 2. Februar 2000 (Stand am 1. Dezember 2013)

⁷ 1 kVA = 0.8 kW; 30 kVA = 24 kW

The two Councils are presently also discussing a change in the tax deduction scheme. Already now investments in energy efficiency of existing buildings including the installation of (BI)PV can be deducted from the tax relevant income of natural persons. But so far the investment can only be deducted in the year in which the investment billed. The Councils are discussing the option, that the deductions could be spread over several years to make big renovation investments executed in one step more attractive.

2.2.2 Long term strategy: transition from subsidies to taxes

In a second phase of Energy Strategy 2050, the Federal Council aims to replace the existing incentive system mainly based on subsidies with incentive mechanisms based on energy and CO₂-taxes. According to the Energy Strategy 2050 the Federal Council proposes a new article in the federal constitution which allows for this transition.⁸ The transition to a system of tax incentives is supposed to start in 2021. The constitutional article (draft) defines a phasing-out of the existing subsidy schemes for renewable energy (in particular the feed-in remuneration at cost) during 10 years after the tax incentive mechanisms have been implemented. Granted feed-in remunerations can be paid until the end of 2045 at the latest. The incentives are based on climate and electricity taxes. The taxes should be levied on fossil combustibles and electricity. The tax revenues shall be redistributed to the general public and to the companies. The amount of the taxes levied will be defined in accordance to the deviation from the energy and climate related goals of the Federation. In model calculations the (draft) dispatch text to the new constitutional article suggests a tax on electricity of 4.5 ct./kWh to reach the energy related goals⁹. Such a tax would favor households that can use a big part of on-site generated PV power instead of buying taxed power from the grid.

2.3 National laws and policy instruments

Photovoltaic technologies profit from the effort the public authorities are making in the view of Energy Strategy 2050 to foster electricity generation by renewable energy sources. The following instruments are already implemented on national level to support PV deployment. Besides the national support activities there are selected additional subsidies for (BI)PV by some cantons or municipalities¹⁰.

2.3.1 PV installation on roofs without building permit

Since 2014 the national law on spatial planning (Raumplanungsgesetz, RPG 700, Art. 18a) stipulates that solar installations on roofs do not need a building permit if the building stands in a building zone or in a farming zone. The installation only has to be reported to

⁸ <https://www.news.admin.ch/message/index.html?lang=de&msg-id=59257> (status quo 15.12.2015)

⁹ 15.xxx Botschaft zum Verfassungsartikel über ein Klima- und Energielenkungssystem vom ... (28.10.2015)

¹⁰ Swissolar provides an overview of all PV-promotion in cantons and municipalities: http://www.swissolar.ch/fileadmin/user_upload/Bauherren/Infodossier_Foerderung_PV.pdf (status quo 10.6.2016)

the authorities. Only if the building is considered an architectural, cultural or natural monument, a building permit is requested. The law allows for the cantons to define particular zones in building zones with little sensitivity in which also non-roof installations can be built without a building permit. This means that whether PV installations on the façade can be implemented without building permit depends on the cantonal laws.

2.3.2 Feed-in remuneration at cost

Feed-in remuneration or tariff at cost (FRC, in German: KEV – Kostendeckende Einspeisevergütung; in French: RPC - Rétribution à prix coûtant) is a policy instrument that was developed by the federal government for the purpose of fostering electricity generation from renewable energy sources. It covers the difference between the production cost and the market price, and guarantees producers of electricity from renewable sources a price that corresponds to their production costs. This promotion instrument started in 2009 and has further been pursued due to the Energy Strategy 2050. Feed-in tariff at cost is available for photovoltaics with an installed capacity from 10 kilowatt upwards. The associated fund is fed by contributions from all electricity consumers, who pay a fee per consumed kilowatt hour.¹¹

The tariff is applicable for 20 years. The tariff rates are subject to a regular review due to technological progress, increasing degree of market maturity and decreasing costs of the PV technology. Reductions on FRC tariffs only apply to new production facilities that are put into operation. Due to the great demand, there is a long waiting list for the feed-in remuneration at cost. For people applying only now for the FRC, there is little chance of still being subsidized by this programme, even though the fee per consumed kilowatt hour will be raised from 1.3 (status quo 1.1.2016) to 1.5 ct. (starting on 1.1.2017) to 2.3 ct. per kWh, according to the discussions in the Federal Councils on the initial package of measures of the Swiss Energy Strategy 2050.

The FRC will be reduced again by 1st of April 2016 and 1st of October 2016.¹² Hence, starting 1st of octobere 2016 the feed-in remuneration for PV installations from 30 to 100 kW_{peak} will be 15.6 ct./kWh¹³. The Swiss Federal Office of Energy SFOE is recommending a minimum feed-in tariff for PV power not integrated in the feed-in remuneration at cost system (market price) of between 6 to 10 ct./kWh¹⁴. But a recent study shows, that the effectively paid tariffs range between 3.5 to 25 ct./kWh with an average of 10 ct./kWh¹⁵.

The feed-in remuneration at cost scheme will probably be replaced by a scheme, in which the producers have to sell their production directly on the market. The National Council and the Council of States still have to come to a common agreement on the details. In the new

¹¹ <http://www.bfe.admin.ch/themen/00612/02073/index.html?lang=de> (status quo 14.12.2015)

¹² news.admin. Bundesrat senkt Vergütungssätze für Photovoltaik-Anlagen. Bern, 11.11.2015

¹³ EnV 730.01. Appendix 1.2, chapter 3.1.3

¹⁴ Bundesamt für Energie 2015 and Stickelberger et al. 2015

¹⁵ Fischer D. 2016

scheme the power producers will get a feed-in premium and a remuneration for the marketing of their electricity generated (marketing premium: Bewirtschaftungsentgelt). The goal of this adapted approach is a power supply which is better synchronized with demand. The additional fees (feed-in premium and marketing premium) will assure the compensation of the ecological value of PV power (for more explanations on this scheme see chapter 2.6 «International regulations and trends»).

Small PV installations will probably still be entitled to get a one-off investment grant or possibly a fixed-term contract with feed-in remuneration at cost. If Switzerland would establish a minimum installation size of 100 kW_{peak} for the obligation to take part in the new marketing premium scheme (that is the threshold Germany applies for their market premium scheme, see chapter 2.6 «International regulations and trends»), most PV installations will not be affected by the new scheme. In the years 2012 to 2014 93% of all new PV installations in Switzerland were smaller than 100 kW_{peak}, 85% smaller than 50 kW_{peak}¹⁶. PV plants with 100 kW_{peak} and more contributed 58% to the newly installed power, the smaller plants 42%.

2.3.3 One-off investment grants

One-off investment grants (in German: Einmalvergütung) are a new instrument that has also been developed by the Confederation for the purpose of encouraging electricity production in small photovoltaic systems (<30 kW_{peak}). One-off investment grants cover a maximum of 30% of the investment costs of reference systems.¹⁷

Photovoltaic systems with an output of 2 to 10 kW_{peak} are subsidised with a one-off grant rather than receiving feed-in remuneration at cost. Operators of photovoltaic systems with an output of between 10 kW_{peak} to 30 kW_{peak} can choose between feed-in remuneration at cost or a one-off grant. The two Councils want to abolish the cap of 30 kW in the frame of their discussion concerning the initial package of measures in line with the Energy Strategy 2050. The new law will allow the Federal Council to define a power cap if necessary¹⁸. The two Councils will probably decide on a limitation in time for the one-off investment grants until 2031¹⁹.

While the tariffs for the feed-in remuneration at cost will be reduced in 2016 again, the one-off grants stay unchanged at least until March 2017.²⁰

- Attached installation: CHF 1'400.- plus CHF 500.- per kW_{peak} installed power.
- Integrated installation: CHF 1'800.- plus CHF 610.- per kW_{peak} installed power (EnV 730.1, Anhang 1.8).

¹⁶ Hostettler 2012, Hostettler 2013, Hostettler 2014

¹⁷ Bundesamt für Energie 2016a

¹⁸ Mutation of Art. 28 in the draft to the new energy law.

http://www.parlament.ch/ab/frameset/d/n/4916/451919/d_n_4916_451919_451920.htm (status quo 15.2.2016)

¹⁹ Bundesamt für Energie 2016b

²⁰ news.admin. Bundesrat senkt Vergütungssätze für Photovoltaik-Anlagen. Bern, 11.11.2015

For an integrated installation with 10 kW_{peak} the financial support is CHF 7'900.-, which is CHF 790.- per kW_{peak}.

2.3.4 Self-consumption

The national law on energy (Energiegesetz EnG SR 730.0) defines the right of every producer of photovoltaic power to self-consume the electricity generated by his/her photovoltaic installation on-site. The surplus electricity after self-consumption that is fed into the grid has to be remunerated according to EnG Art. 7 Abs.2²¹.

This regulation can be financially interesting for on-site consumers since the share of self-consumed PV electricity substitutes electricity from the grid at the corresponding costs (comprising production and grid costs). Excess electricity generation not being consumed on-site will be remunerated according to EnG Art. 7 Abs. 2 at the costs avoided by the utility for corresponding electricity purchases (wholesale price) typically resulting in much a lower unit remuneration (official recommendation: CHF 0.06 to 0.1 per kWh). So far the costs for grid installation and maintenance etc. are generally covered by fees raised per kilowatt hour consumed from the grid.

To date prosumers (prosumers are at the same time «consumer» and «producer» of electric power) don't pay any extra grid access fees. But this scheme is recently being questioned since a strongly increasing share of prosumers being still connected to the grid and still having about the same remaining demand for peak-power and grid capacity endangers cost recovery for grid investments and operation by the traditional pricing model which passes on grid costs mainly by a kilowatt hour tariff. Self-consumption of PV electricity will decrease grid revenues, while local and regional grid costs decrease not to the same extent. Hence, some electricity system operators think about changing their pricing models for prosumers, e.g. by putting prosumers in a separate tariff group, newly charging a fee for the peak electric power (kW) demanded by the individual prosumer. Such pricing models endanger financial viability of PV and self-consumption and counteract (BI)PV-subsidy programs (Rechsteiner 2016). If additionally metering of the load profiles is required by the grid operator prohibitive metering costs tend to aggravate the economic barriers for (BI)PV deployment and self-consumption.

2.3.5 Purchase guarantee

While the producer is free to consume as much electricity as possible on-site, the electricity system operator is obliged to buy the excess electricity fed into his grid²². Due to this law, small producers do not incur any disadvantage. This obligation will be abandoned at least for bigger plants once the incentive mechanisms and the adapted feed-in system with feed-in premium instead of feed-in tariffs at cost are implemented.

²¹ Art. 7 Abs. 2bis and Art. 7a Abs. 4b EnG

²² Art. 7 Abs. 1 and Art. 7a Abs. 1 EnG

2.4 Model regulations of the cantons for energy matters (MuKEEn/MoPEEC)

The Swiss Confederation is responsible for most energy related policy issues in Switzerland except for the building sector. In the building sector the cantons are responsible for the laws and regulations concerning energy. The cantons coordinate their activities via the conference of cantonal energy ministers (Konferenz Kantonaler Energiedirektoren, EnDK). The fundamentals are provided by the conference of cantonal energy offices (Konferenz Kantonaler Energiefachstellen, EnFK). In 1992 the cantons came forward with the first «cantonal model regulations for energy matters» (MuKEEn/MoPEEC). At the moment the MuKEEn/MoPEEC 2008 are in force. In January 2015 the EnDK approved the MuKEEn/MoPEEC 2014 which should be translated to cantonal law in all cantons by 2020. Due to the national requirements the cantons are supposed to implement the basic modules (Basismodule) of the MuKEEn/MoPEEC literally in cantonal law. The optional modules of the MuKEEn can be added voluntarily but would have to be implemented literally too²³. Even though the cantonal energy ministers have approved the MuKEEn/MoPEEC 2014, their implementation into cantonal law is not guaranteed. The changes have to pass the cantonal parliaments, what means that political opposition can prevent the implementation.

2.4.1 MuKEEn/MoPEEC 2008 and PV

In the MuKEEn/MoPEEC from 2008 there are no modules with direct impact on BIPV or PV. The MuKEEn 2008 stipulates for every new building and building extensions that at least 20% of the heating demand has to be covered by renewable energy resources. Several of the proposed standard solutions contained solar thermic installations but not photovoltaic installations.

2.4.2 MuKEEn/MoPEEC 2014 and PV

MuKEEn/MoPEEC 2014 contains two basic modules that directly influence BIPV and PV and one basic module that indirectly affects them.

Direct impact:

- Every new building has to generate part of its electricity demand on-site (basic modul E)
- If a fossil heating system is replaced, at least 10% of the heating energy demand must be covered by renewable energies (basic modul F)

Indirect impact:

- Centrally operated electric waterheaters have to be replaced within the next 15 years (basic modul I)

²³ These chapters on MuKEEn are based on the following sources: Konferenz Kantonaler Energiedirektoren (Hrsg.): Mustervorschriften der Kantone im Energiebereich (MuKEEn), Ausgabe 2008, Konferenz Kantonaler Energiedirektoren (Hrsg.): Mustervorschriften der Kantone im Energiebereich (MuKEEn), Ausgabe 2014, deutsche Version, 9.1.2015 and on an internal paper draft of Cyril Studer, HSLU.

Every new building has to generate part of its electricity demand on-site (basic modul E)

Basic Modul E does not stipulate which type of power production installation has to be implemented. With a photovoltaic installation the code might be fulfilled at the lowest price. Required power the installation has to provide is at least 10 W per m² heated area but not more than 30 kW in total²⁴.

The cantons are free to define the amount of the compensation payment if no electricity is produced on-site. The MuKE n suggests CHF 1'000.- per kW missing power.

What is not decided yet is the question whether subsidies for PV (feed-in remuneration at cost, one-off investment grants etc.) can still be granted for new buildings once MuKE n/MoPEC 2014 is implemented. So far financial support is only granted to activities and installations that are not required by law.

Furthermore, the success of this module for promoting (BI)PV depends a lot on the amount of the compensation payment. If the payment is too low, building owners will prefer to pay instead of installing PV on their building.

Replacement of a fossil heating system requiring at least 10% renewable energy (basic modul F)

Basic Modul F requires that in case of a heating replacement the new system must cover at least 10% of the heating demand by renewable energy sources. If the building owner does not choose to switch entirely to a system with renewable energy there are eleven standard solutions he/her can choose from to meet the 10% requirement.

Standard solution SL1 contains a thermal solar installation for the water heating system of at least 2% of the total heated area as minimally installed area of thermal solar.

Standard solution SL 7 contains a heat pump water heater with photovoltaic installation of at least 5 W_p/m² heated area.

Replacement of central electric waterheaters within the next 15 years (basic modul I)

This basic module might have a similar effect on the PV-market as may have basic modul F. One possible solution for the replacement of a central electric water heater could be a heat pump water heater with photovoltaic installation. But this is not explicitly mentioned in MuKE n 2014. MuKE n 2014 rather implies that the building owners should have enough time to replace the water heater together with the heating system referred to in basic modul F once the old heating system is to be replaced.

2.4.3 MuKE n/MoPEC 2014: Implications for BIPV

The MuKE n/MoPEC 2014, especially the basis modul E which requires electricity production in every new building, has the potential to foster (BI)PV deployment in the next decade. But even though the MuKE n 2014 has been approved by the cantonal energy ministers, the implementation by the cantons is still at risk. The regulation has to be transferred into cantonal law which requires political majorities that have to be attained first. It is to be said

²⁴ The cap is relevant for buildings with more than 3'000 m² energy consumption area.

that all MuKE/MoPEC modules will rather favour PV than BIPV, since PV is the cheaper option in most of the cases.

But MuKE/MoPEC 2014 underlines the understanding that every building should contribute to the national electricity production. The more common this understanding becomes the better also for BIPV.

2.5 Support for PV by the cantons

The national subsidy program for energy related building renovation (Gebäudeprogramm) focuses on energy efficiency improvements mainly at the building envelope and does not foster building technologies like heating systems or photovoltaic installations. National subsidies for renewable electricity generation are mainly based on the feed-in remuneration at cost system and on one-off investment grants. It is the cantons which support deployment of renewable energy production technologies to a differing extent with own subsidy programs.

Since the case studies and the technology transfer projects within the «Active Interfaces» project are located in the canton of Neuchâtel (case studies) and the canton of Lucern (technology transfer projects), the subsidy programs for PV installation of these two cantons are presented here²⁵.

Neither the canton of Neuchâtel nor the canton of Lucerne does financially subsidize photovoltaic installations on buildings.

Additionally, the investment in a new PV installation on an existing building can be deducted from the tax relevant income of natural persons within the federal income tax as well as within most of the cantonal and communal income taxes. The canton of Lucern and the canton of Graubünden are the only cantons where investments for PV installations on existing buildings can not be deducted from the tax relevant income in the corresponding cantonal taxes.

The canton of Lucern has elaborated a list of design criteria for PV installations. If a PV installation fulfills these criteria there is no need for a building permit for the PV installation²⁶. The text suggests that installations on the roof are to be preferred to ones on the façade. Only if the PV installation on the façade is an integral part of the architecture it can be preferred to a roof installation. The design criteria list contains criteria for roof and façade installations.

The canton of Neuchâtel does not provide own criteria. Its webpage refers to the criteria defined in the national law on spatial planning and the according ordinances²⁷.

²⁵ For subsidy programs in other cantons and municipalities see: http://www.swissolar.ch/fileadmin/user_upload/Bauherren/Infodossier_Foerderung_PV.pdf

²⁶ Kanton Luzern 2015

²⁷ <http://www.ne.ch/autorites/DDTE/SCAT/pc-zb/Pages/accueil.aspx> (status quo 12.2.2016)

2.6 International regulations and trends

To date the EU aims at a share of 20% of the energy consumed in the European Union in 2020 from renewable sources (and at least 27% by 2030). Promotion of this objective throughout Europe has led to a spectacular increase in the production capacity of renewable energy sources. In 2011 over 100 gigawatts of solar panels were installed worldwide, 70 % thereof in the EU.²⁸

Germany has a leading role in fostering energy production from renewable resources in the EU. The support of renewable energy sources is the core element of German energy and climate policy. Subsidies on grounds of the Renewable Energy Source Act (Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz, EEG) with feed-in tariffs have proven most effective in fostering power production from renewable energy sources²⁹. The German feed-in tariff system has been the model for the Swiss feed-in remuneration at cost system (KEV).

In 2012 the feed-in tariff scheme in Germany has been complemented by a market premium scheme (EEG 2012). Feed-in **tariffs** are paid independently from market prices. In a feed-in **premium** model the **market price** for electricity influences total remuneration. The goal of the change in the remuneration scheme is a more demand-driven energy generation. Since 2014 in the EU direct marketing of renewable energy sources is mandatory except for small plants (EEG 2014). By 2016 only installations with a capacity of less than 100 kW_{peak} can stay in the feed-in tariff system without direct marketing. For bigger plants the sliding market premium has been established as the new primary instrument to support deployment of renewable energy sources in Germany³⁰.

Purkus et al. (2015) present a critical analysis of the feed-in premium scheme in Germany. Direct marketing has made a positive contribution to better integrating dispatchable renewable energy sources (e. g. biomass) into the market. For intermittent renewable energy sources as PV the most important effect is a voluntary curtailment of production in times of negative electricity prices and thus reducing the load burden of the grid. The study mentions the necessity of further developing the incentive mechanisms. It also mentions that the transformation of the electricity system cannot be reached through renewable energy sources market integration only. Flexibilisation incentives are needed for other participants in the electricity market too, e. g. for coal-fired power plants.

Switzerland aims to implement a feed-in premium scheme too. It should consist of a feed-in premium (Einspeiseprämie) and a marketing premium (Bewirtschaftungsentgelt). The exact design is still being discussed (see also chapter 2.3.2 «Feed-in remuneration at cost»).

²⁸ The EU explained: Energy. European Commission, Nov. 2014 (ISBN 978-92-79-42192-1) Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2014

²⁹ Entwicklung eines Fördersystems für die Vermarktung von erneuerbarer Stromerzeugung Themenbereich 4. Frank SENSFUSS, Mario RAGWITZ, Fraunhofer Institut System - und Innovationsforschung, Karlsruhe 2009

³⁰ Purkus et al. Energy, Sustainability and Society (2015) 5:12. Market integration of renewable energies through direct marketing - lessons learned from the German market premium scheme. Alexandra Purkus, Erik Gawel, Marc Deissenroth, Kristina Nienhaus, Sandra Wassermann

PV installation in Switzerland on private buildings will rarely exceed 100 kW_{peak} installed power, most of them will stay below 50 kW_{peak}. Therefore it is possible, that BIPV will not be obliged to switch to the market premium scheme but can continue on fixed feed-in tariffs. But at the time being, there is an extremely long waiting list for PV-projects applying for feed-in tariffs at cost. It is not clear yet whether there will still be enough funds for all plants entitled for subsidies, if the fee per consumed kilowatt hour, with which the subsidies are financed and the share of funds allocated to PV subsidies are not raised again.

3 Trends and goals for future policies

3.1 Future financial support for PV

The existing feed-in tariff at cost promotion program for photovoltaic installations in Switzerland will be amended. The National Council and the Council of States are still discussing the details. It might be changed to or complemented by a marketing premium scheme similar to the one in Germany.

The discussions in the Councils so far indicate that there will probably be the option for all PV plants to choose a one-off investment grant. But anyhow the financial support will drop continuously due to sinking costs for PV installations.

But the Swiss Energy Strategy 2050, its initial package and the planned transition to a system of management of demand by taxes instead of subsidies are currently at risk and tend to be jeopardised by the majority prevailing in the parliament since autumn 2015. The vote on the phasing-out-of-nuclear-energy-initiative of the Green Party will show how the voting majority of the Swiss population will see the future of the Swiss energy system. If the initiative will be rejected or only poorly agreed in the referendum (probably in autumn 2016) the currently prevailing parliament majority might feel confirmed in the curtailment of the Swiss Energy Strategy 2050.

3.2 Storage as the new topic

The combination of PV installations with on-site or local electricity storage capacities to compensate for the intermittent PV production is getting rising attention. The canton of Thurgau does subsidize batteries for the storage of PV electricity. There might be some energy suppliers that also subsidize storage solutions but it is not yet a widespread policy. Technology development and cost reductions in the storage sector are ongoing and at the time being the most promising storage technologies have not clearly emerged yet. In the wake of new business opportunities for balancing energy in the electric grid combined with decreasing battery costs, batteries will probably get more attention. In Germany there are already suppliers of swarm storage facilities (Schwarmspeicher). They use parts of the storage capacities in private PV batteries to pool the capacities (swarm) to create balancing energy capacities for the grid.

The development of electric vehicles can foster PV deployment. Ideally electric vehicles will be charged during peak PV electricity production periods at noon or the batteries of parked vehicles serve as storage for PV electricity. There are efforts on different levels to replace fossil fuel cars by electric vehicles: Norway for instance plans to ban all fossil fuel cars by 2025. Some Swiss municipalities promote actively charging stations for electric vehicles.

3.3 Passing on of grid costs

With a rising share of intermittent renewable power production the inclination will increase to request remuneration from the PV power producers for grid connection since the traditional pricing model for residential end users might not allow full grid cost recovery for the connection of prosumers any more. There will have to be a political discussion on how to distribute fairly the costs of grid connection comprising the construction, operation and maintenance of the regional electricity grids. So far the grid costs are levied on the power consumed by the end users on CHF per kWh basis. But prosumer-households (prosumers are at the same time «consumer» and «producer» of electric power) consume relatively little power from the grid – and even less, if battery storage is available and economical viable. At the same time prosumer-households still profit from the grid for selling their surplus power production via grid, for grid power in periods with low renewable generation, for the grid services and the provision of backup capacities to compensate for intermittent renewable electricity generation. Thereby their individual peak load demanded from the grid will not decrease (unless they will have large local storage capacities) and local grid cost savings due to prosumers will be smaller than the loss of revenues for the grid operator by self-consumption of prosumers. Therefore the more prosumer-households, the bigger is the cost share the remaining consumer-households have to carry or the higher is the loss of revenues for the grid operator. The political discussion on how to deal with this newly emerging cost allocation problem is just being started³¹.

This can lead to lower remuneration of fed-in electricity and/or to a fee for grid connection. Such a fee could depend for instance on the peak power of on-site installed renewable generation capacity. Besides it might be that the purchase guarantee for intermittently generated renewable electricity will be at least partially released or that intermittent renewable producers are integrated into balancing of local electricity demand and supply. This would reduce revenues from PV electricity generation and tends to make the installation of PV unattractive.

In a recent study (Rechsteiner 2016) it is argued that in Switzerland self-consumption in reality will only marginally influence the coverage of the grid costs. The advantages of more prosumer-households for the power grid and in view of Energy Strategy 2050 on the other hand prevail by far. To render PV production for private home owners less attractive would stop the expansion of PV installations that could be observed during the recent years thanks to a sharp drop in prices and thanks to promotion efforts of the authorities. But the study (Rechsteiner 2016) does not take into account that prosumers do not really contribute to reduce necessary grid capacities since the intermittent character of PV generation doesn't allow for reducing capacity demand from the grid, except if large local storage capacities can insure power supply in bad weather periods with no or hardly any supply of PV power.

³¹ Hettich et al. 2015

4 Policy assumptions for Active Interfaces

In the «Active Interfaces» project, different packages of building renovation measures will be compared and assessed.

We suggest the following **set of assumptions** for the assessments in the «Active Interfaces» project. The assumptions apply if their topic is relevant for the case studies or the technology transfer projects and if it is relevant for the comparative life cycle cost analyses:

- We assume that MuKE n/MoPEC 2014 has already been integrated into the cantonal energy laws. .
- In basic modul E (every new building has to generate part of its electricity demand on-site) a compensation payment of CHF 1'000.- per kW_{peak} required will be charged in all cantons if the requirement to locally generate is not fully fulfilled.
- We assume that the threshold for the one-off investment grants has already been cancelled. Therefore, all PV projects should be assessed with one-off investment grants and the according financial support applicable today (February 2016):

		until 31.3.2017	1.4.2017 until 30.9.2017	starting on 1.10.2017
Attached in-stallation	fix	1'400.- CHF	1'400.- CHF	1'400.- CHF
	variable	500.- CHF/kW _{peak}	450.- CHF/kW _{peak}	400.- CHF/kW _{peak}
Integrated in-stallation	fix	1'800.- CHF	1'700.- CHF	1'600.- CHF
	variable	610.- CHF/kW _{peak}	540.- CHF/kW _{peak}	460.- CHF/kW _{peak}

Tabelle 1: Assumed one-off investment grants according to the draft of the new energy ordinance (Energieverordnung EnV 730.01)

- We assume that there will still be a purchase guarantee for excess power produced by PV plants. For the time being (March 2016) the feed-in price (without FRC) assumption is 14 ct./kWh for plants in the city of Lucerne, 15 ct./kWh in the city of Neuchâtel starting in 2016³². We propose to distinguish for the feed-in prices two different perspectives:

Perspective of the particular building owner: The assessment is done with the currently offered feed-in tariff, i.e. 14 ct./kWh in Lucerne and 15 ct./kWh in Neuchâtel.

Perspective of the policy maker: The assessment should be more independent of the specific location of the assessed building. Therefore, a national feed-in price according to the derived feed-in price in «Common methodological frame-work to assess energy, climate and economic impacts of BIPV» (Ott et al. 2016) is assumed: 6.2 ct./kWh plus 2.0 ct./kWh for the added ecological value = 8.2 ct./kWh. The price development follows the assumptions established in table 1 of «Common methodological frame-work to assess energy, climate and economic impacts of BIPV» (Ott et al. 2016).

³² According to the actual price for fed-in PV power: www.pvtarif.ch (status quo 4.3.2016)

- For an estimation of the revenues from the PV power generated on-site, we assume the following solution: the on-site generated PV power is sold by the owner of the PV installation to the tenants at the average national price for the SFOE-tariff category H4: 20.6 ct./kWh³³. We assume that in the case studies the meters for determining the self-consumption and the corresponding revenues for on-site generated and on-site consumed power will be installed. The excess power is fed-in to the grid and remunerated as mentioned above.
- Initial investment costs of PV installations on existing buildings can be deducted from the income of natural persons for the federal taxes and for the cantonal taxes in Neuchâtel. In the canton of Lucerne it can't be deducted from the cantonal taxes. The effect on the taxes is heavily depending on the income of the building owner (usually in the range of 10% to 30% of the investment costs). Therefore, in the frame of the Active Interfaces assessments the tax-effect is not taken into account.
- All assessments are made for the case of no subsidies and no tax deductions as well as for the case with the above mentioned subsidies but without tax deductions to have a cost assessment from the perspective of the society and policy maker as well as a cost assessment from the perspective of the investor and owner of the particular building.

³³ <https://www.strompreis.elcom.admin.ch/Map/ShowSwissMap.aspx> (status quo 10.6.2016)

Literatur

Primärliteratur

Bundesgesetz über die Raumplanung (Raumplanungsgesetz, RPG) 700. vom 22. Juni 1979 (Stand am 1. Januar 2016)

Raumplanungsverordnung (RPV) vom 28. Juni 2000 (Stand am 1. Januar 2015) 700.1

Energieverordnung (EnV) 730.01. vom 7. Dezember 1998 (Stand am 1. Januar 2016)

Energiegesetz Entwurf (EnG) vom ...Entwurf vom 4.9.2013

Sekundärliteratur

Bundesamt für Energie (2016a): Faktenblatt Einmalvergütung und Eigenverbrauch für kleine Photovoltaik-Anlagen Version 4.1 vom 22. Januar 2016; Bern

Bundesamt für Energie (2016b): ENERGIESTRATEGIE 2050: Stand vor der Zweitberatung im Nationalrat, Medienhintergrundgespräch; Steinmann W., Previdoli P., Bern, 19.02. 2016

Bundesamt für Energie (2015): Vollzugshilfe für die Umsetzung der Anschlussbedingungen der Elektrizitätsproduktion gemäss Art. 7 und Art. 28a des Energiegesetzes (EnG; SR 730.0). Version 2.1. Bundesamt für Energie. Januar 2015, Bern

Bundesrat (2013): 13.074 Botschaft zum ersten Massnahmenpaket der Energiestrategie 2050 (Revision des Energierechts) und zur Volksinitiative «Für den geordneten Ausstieg aus der Atomenergie (Atomausstiegsinitiative)» vom 4. September 2013, Bern

European Union (2014): The EU explained: Energy. European Commission, Nov. 2014 (ISBN 978-92-79-42192-1) Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2014

Fischer D. (2016): Solarstrom: mehr oder weniger willkommen? Pressemitteilung VESE - Verband unabhängiger Energieerzeuger. 22.2.2016

Hettich P., Walther S., Wohlgemuth D. (2015): Investitionen ins Verteilnetz: Rechtliche Grundlagen und Anreize bei zunehmender Eigenproduktion. EGI Working Papers Series (No. 4), 2015

Hostettler T. (2013): Markterhebung Sonnenenergie 2012. Teilstatistik der Schweizerischen Statistik der erneuerbaren Energien. SWISSOLAR im Auftrag des Bundesamts für Energie, Zürich, Juni 2013

Hostettler T. (2014): Markterhebung Sonnenenergie 2013. Teilstatistik der Schweizerischen Statistik der erneuerbaren Energien. SWISSOLAR im Auftrag des Bundesamts für Energie, Zürich, Juli 2014

Hostettler T. (2015): Markterhebung Sonnenenergie 2014: Teilstatistik der Schweizerischen Statistik der erneuerbaren Energien; SWISSOLAR, im Auftrag des Bundesamts für Energie, Zürich, Juni 2015

Kanton Luzern (2015): Richtlinien. Solaranlagen. Ausgabe Dezember 2015

Ott W., Lehmann M. (2016): Common methodological frame-work to assess energy, climate and economic impacts of BIPV; Zürich. 30.6. 2016

Purkus et al. Energy, Sustainability and Society (2015): Market integration of renewable energies through direct marketing - lessons learned from the German market premium scheme; Alexandra Purkus, Erik Gawel, Marc Deissenroth, Kristina Nienhaus, Sandra Wassermann

Rechsteiner R. (2016): Diskriminierende Tarifstrukturen – es droht ein Ausbaustopp der Photovoltaik. resolution.ch for swissolar, Basel, 2.2016

Sensfuss F., Ragwitz M. (2009): Entwicklung eines Fördersystems für die Vermarktung von erneuerbarer Stromerzeugung Themenbereich 4. Fraunhofer Institut System- und Innovationsforschung; Karlsruhe, 2009

Stickelberger D., Moll C. (2015): Soll ich die Kostendeckende Einspeisevergütung (KEV) oder die Einmalvergütung (EIV) wählen? SWISSOLAR, Zürich, 3.3.2015